

Correction to Van Pham et al's original article "Using text-matching software in educational science research: Research results from 18 universities in Vietnam". DOI: 10.3897/ese.2023.e107484
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ARTICLE CORRECTION

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In this article, the Methods subsection of the Abstract has been corrected to accurately reflect the data collection methods used in the study, and now reads "This study employed a mixed-methods approach, including quantitative analysis of survey data collected from 104 researchers across 18 universities in Vietnam regarding their use of text-matching software, as well as a qualitative analysis of plagiarism-related regulations in scientific research at seven universities and seven representative educational science journals in Vietnam."

In the Methods section, an ethics statement was not included. The following statement has been added to the Methods: "The research has been approved by the National Foundation for Science and Technology Development (NAFOSTED) under the Ministry of Science and Technology of Vietnam, in 2020, and complies with the ethics regulations of the University of Education – Vietnam National University, Hanoi (No.: 180/QĐ-HĐQLNAFOSTED).

The study was exempted from institutional review board approval owing to the data collection methods used (surveys), according to the regulation specified in Article 6, Section 4, and Article 8 of the university's regulations on the organisation and operation of the Research Ethics Committee, qualifying it for exemption from ethics committee review. Participants were informed about the purpose of the study and guaranteed anonymity and, by participating in the survey, gave their consent for participation in the study."

These corrections have been made to the online article. DOI: 10.3897/ese.2023.e107484